

mBatik Space: Developing Experiential Learning Framework for Intangible Cultural Heritage Preservation

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ABSTRACT

Batik, an intangible cultural heritage of Indonesia, faces a challenge in its preservation due to widespread promotion but inadequate craftsmen regeneration. This paper proposes *mBatik Space*, a Batik preservation exhibit that aims to transfer the Batik craftsmanship skills to the next generation. Though hands-on classes to learn the skills to create Batik is not a new concept, as evident in Kampung Batik Kauman and Kampung Batik Laweyan in Surakarta, *mBatik Space* differentiates itself by following more closely to the theory of experiential learning as its framework. With experiential learning as a baseline, the exhibit emphasizes participants' independence in the learning process through a cycle of inquiry, problem-solving, and discovery. By empowering youth as active participants in Batik production, rather than passive consumers, the exhibit offers hope for the continuity of Batik heritage for future generations.

Keywords: *Batik, intangible cultural heritage, cultural preservation, experiential learning, mBatik Space*

1. INTRODUCTION

Batik — an over-promoted yet under-maintained cultural form from Indonesia. UNESCO in 2009 recognized it as an intangible cultural heritage of humanity for its complexity and the skills it takes to create it (UNESCO, 2009). Creating one fabric of Batik could take months if done manually. It starts with *nyanting*, a process where a pattern is drawn onto the fabric using wax

and a pen-like tool called *canting*. Continues with coloring the fabric, either with a brush or by dipping the fabric into the dye, and then removing the excess wax. The process could be repeated multiple times if needed (Susanti & Azhar, 2020). Experts Batik craftsmen, who are now mostly 40 to 60 years old, spent most of their lives honing their skills in this field (Suliyanto et al., 2015; Tugu Jogja, 2022; Pandangan Jogja, 2023; Baihaqi, 2023). A number of them are known to meditate, pray, and fast before creating Batik, particularly when they are designing a new pattern. This is due to the belief that every line and dot drawn has a meaning of its own, which must come from the tranquil state of mind of its creators (Probosiwi et al., 2021). Thus Batik is a much more holistic cultural form than it is usually thought of, integrating arts and wellness into its creation process.

The significance of the process of creating Batik must be taken into consideration in its preservation by focusing on skill transfer and craftsmen regeneration rather than just preserving the preexisting Batik. Thus experiential learning becomes the most fitting way to preserve the Batik-making skills. Kolb's experiential learning theory, as elaborated by McCarthy (2010), suggests that knowledge is learned most effectively through grasping and transforming experiences into action.

The problem is that most Batik preservation efforts in Indonesia focus on merely promoting Batik as objects. A key figure who shaped this status quo of Batik preservation is Soeharto, the second president of Indonesia. In the 1960s, he made it mandatory for civil servants to wear Batik as one of their uniforms and this custom remains today (Budiono, 2016; Ardanareswari, 2019). It was also his habit to give Batik to foreign dignitaries who visited Indonesia, notably the former President of the United States, Ronald Reagan, and the former President of South Africa, Nelson Mandela (Ardanareswari, 2019). The idea behind President Soeharto's policies was that Batik should be appreciated by being seen and worn as much as possible. This idea is still applied in today's efforts and trends, even when 60 years have passed.

As a result, when high consumption of Batik is not balanced with an equally high production

through skill transfer, these strategies further harm Batik's sustainability. Current Batik craftsmen are predominantly 40 years old and above, without much youth working in the industry for sufficient regeneration (Tugu Jogja, 2022; Pandangan Jogja, 2023; Baihaqi, 2023). The problem has been amplified since the pandemic, as the Association of Indonesian Batik Craftsmen and Entrepreneurs (APPBI) noted a significant decrease in the number of Batik craftsmen. Out of a total of 151 thousand Batik craftsmen, only 37 thousand were active (Wiratama, 2021). When this lack of regeneration continues to happen and the production of traditionally made Batik decreases, it would normalize the utilization of factory-made Batik that doesn't use wax or *canting* and instead only prints the pattern directly on the fabric. This further harms the preservation of Batik as it ruins its authenticity.

Therefore, this research proposed '*mBatik Space*', an exhibit aimed at Batik preservation through experiential learning. The design of this exhibit will evaluate and consider existing Batik-making classes and improve them to emphasize the keys of experiential learning, such as problem-solving, discovery, and inquiry. Through *mBatik Space*, it is hoped that Batik production will be further promoted through skill transfer to the younger generation.

2. DISCUSSION

2. 1. Experiential Learning for Cultural Preservation

Experiential learning is well-regarded in the educational sector due to its approach that encourages learners to take an active role in the learning process (McCarthy, 2010). Some even mention that experiential learning is less of a technique and more of a philosophy of education because it believes that true learning comes from continuously transforming and interpreting one's past experiences, knowledge, and beliefs (Bartle, 2015). According to Anthony, Ewing, Jaynes, and Perkus (1990), there are 6 main characteristics of experiential learning: (1) Directed by students themselves; (2) Emphasizes problem-solving, discovery, and inquiry; (3) Focuses on practical application rather than theoretical explanation; (4) Creates a holistic understanding of the topic; (5) Subjective or perception based, so different learners might gain different insight

from the learning process; (6) Focuses on the heuristics process. Below is a diagram that illustrates the cycle of experiential learning by Kolb, beginning from concrete experience on the topic that stimulates reflective observation which creates conceptualization of the knowledge that would then be applied through active experimentation.

Image 1. Kolb’s experiential learning cycle (Bartle, 2015)

As intangible cultural heritage preservation relies on the transmission of skills and craftsmanship, experiential learning becomes the most suitable approach for it. It has been used to preserve traditional dances in Greece, as dance movement could only be learned through participation and practice (Georgios, 2018). Similarly, a school program in Papua used this approach to introduce its students to traditional pottery (Dabamona & Cater, 2018). The same research stated that there are several benefits to using an experiential learning approach for cultural preservation. Independent observation has proven beneficial to incite personalized insights and unique learning experiences for each of the students, for no two students can have the same insight. Due to this personalized learning experience, the whole process became more emotionally engaging as students mentioned how they were very excited, curious, and happy to explore traditional pottery. Most importantly, the experiential learning approach ignites further curiosity in students to learn more about traditional pottery after the class ends. Proving the approach’s effectiveness to

preserve culture and inherit it to the next generation.

2. 2. Formulation of *mBatik Space*

Designing *mBatik Space* began from observing places that have been providing Batik experiential learning, such as two villages in Surakarta, Indonesia, which have been known for centuries to be centers of Batik production: Kampung Batik Kauman and Kampung Batik Laweyan. This observation aims to find a key element in the experiential learning program of both Batik production centers to be utilized and improved in *mBatik Space*.

Image 2. Kampung Batik Kauman (Fadhilah, 2023)

Located on the west side of the Surakarta Hardiningrat Palace, since the 16th century, Kampung Batik Kauman is home to many *abdi dalem*, servants of Javanese palaces (Indriawati, 2022). As courtiers of the Surakarta royal family, they have retained the traditional way of creating Batik and passed it down from one generation to the next. Though at first, the Batik production in Kauman was to fulfill the palace needs, throughout the decades, the village's Batik gained more and more popularity among the general public (Nurjanah et al., 2021). In 2009, the city government of Surakarta officially declared Kampung Batik Kauman as a Batik tourism village

(Ratriningsih, 2017). As of now, the village is filled with Batik stores that have expanded their businesses by also creating cafes and restaurants to attract more tourists.

Image 3. Kampung Batik Laweyan (Asikin, 2019)

Unlike Kampung Batik Kauman, Kampung Batik Laweyan originated as a production village of *tenun*, a traditional woven fabric, in the 14th century (Hariyani et al., 2007; Anisah & Tohjiwa, 2016). Batik then started to be produced in this village since the heyday of Surakarta Hardiningrat Kingdom in the 17th century. Its purpose was not to fulfill the palace's needs, so the craftsmen of Kampung Batik Laweyan had more freedom to develop more creative Batik patterns. The village was recognized by the city government as a tourism and Batik production center as well as a tangible cultural heritage in 1997. Aside from Batik stores, craftsmen in Kampung Batik Laweyan also opened workshops where tourists can learn how to create Batik.

A shared element in both of these villages is that the workshop aimed to invite visitors to try creating Batik. In one of the Batik stores at Kampung Batik Kauman, half of the building is utilized as a workshop for the craftsmen to create their Batik. Visitors can observe them or take turns *nyanting* or drawing the pattern on the fabric. Craftsmen in Kampung Batik Laweyan took it a step further. A workshop in Kampung Batik Laweyan provides classes that visitors can book to practice the whole process of creating Batik that they can bring home, from drawing the

pattern with a pencil, retracing it using wax, and coloring the fabric. This element supports the idea of experiential learning where a skill is learned through practical application (Anthony et al., 1990).

The experiential learning approach in these villages, however, could be improved further. In both villages, the classes provided are not learner-centered. Participants must follow exactly what the instructor/craftsmen dictate with no room for independent inquiry and experimentation. Additionally, participants are not taught the history of Batik itself and the meanings behind it, so they don't gain a holistic understanding of Batik after the class. These evaluations were taken into consideration when designing *mBatik Space* to provide a better experience for the participants, by emphasizing more on the characteristics of experiential learning.

2. 3. *mBatik Space* as Experiential Learning Program Towards Batik Preservation

mBatik Space is an exhibition where visitors can learn more about Batik and experience the process of creating Batik. The exhibition is conducted in Sekolah Cikal Surabaya supported by the school Student Council, with the targeted visitors being middle school and high school students as well as teachers of the school. However, in its implementation, there were additional visitors from elementary school students and teachers, adding a total of more than 60 visitors.

This exhibit comprises of 4 activities/areas: (1) *Nyanting area*; (2) Batik history exhibit; (3) Batik coloring kit selling booth; and (4) Batik quiz. There is no specific route that visitors must follow in this exhibit to give them a sense of independence in learning about Batik. Typically, the first and second areas are what visitors initially see when they enter the exhibit. If the visitor prefers to learn the theory and history behind Batik, they tend to go to the Batik history exhibit first. If they prefer to immediately try out how to create Batik or *nyanting*, they could visit the *Nyanting* area. The third area is designed to provide additional opportunities for visitors to learn further about Batik by doing the coloring process, as well as to collect funds to donate towards Batik-making classes in other regions in Indonesia. The fourth area, the Batik quiz, is designed to test visitors' knowledge of Batik after visiting all the other areas.

Image 4. *mBatik Space* Layout

The *mBatik Space* evaluation is done through observation and survey. The observation reveals how the experiential learning process in the *Nyanting* area (Image 4) fits Kolb’s cycle (Image 1). Participants enter the area with their past experience or knowledge about Batik or similar art forms such as drawing or painting (Concrete Experience). Most participants typically hesitate to immediately try out *nyanting*, so for several minutes, they tend to observe those who are already *nyanting* or drawing the wax on the fabric (Reflective Observation). From past experiences and observations, participants conceptualize their own understanding of how to do *nyanting* (Abstract Conceptualization). After being sure of their understanding, participants would then try *nyanting* (Active Experimentation). Student Council members, who are involved in the committees of *mBatik Space*, only supervise and give necessary instructions if the participants need it so they would have the opportunity to independently learn. Furthermore, in the survey, participants mentioned that they were more interested in learning about as well as creating Batik after the exhibit. This increased interest is facilitated, and they can learn further about the next process in creating Batik by purchasing Batik coloring kits available on the spot.

Image 5. Kolb’s experiential learning cycle as applied in *mBatik Space*

Overall, the enthusiasm and interest shown by the participants show that there is still hope in transferring the skills of creating Batik to the next generation. The implementation of *mBatik Space* proves that experiential learning provides room for youth to explore more about Batik in a much more engaging way as it offers a sense of independence and control in the learning process. Therefore this program could be a blueprint for future Batik preservation strategies. Empowering youth to get involved in the Batik production process, instead of just a passive consumer.

3. CONCLUSION

mBatik Space is a proposed solution to the necessity of preserving the craftsmanship of Batik and helping the process of Batik craftsmen's regeneration. This initiative, designed as an experiential learning exhibit, not only educates participants about Batik's cultural significance but also actively involves them in the creative process. Experiential learning is proven to be a suitable framework for this exhibit, as it allows participants to independently learn through inquiry, problem-solving, and discovery processes.

The effectiveness of *mBatik Space* in igniting enthusiasm and interest among participants is

demonstrated through observation and survey. The experiential learning cycle is well applied in the process, as participants begin by connecting their past experiences related to Batik with their observation in the exhibit while watching others do *nyanting*, and end with them taking the initiative to learn *nyanting* by themselves. This resulted in participants' increased interest in learning Batik.

In essence, *mBatik Space* represents an innovative approach to Batik preservation, emphasizing the importance of skill transfer and youth engagement. As we embark on this journey to safeguard Batik for future generations, it is important to recognize the power of experiential learning in upholding this cultural heritage.

4. LIMITATIONS

Until its current implementation, *mBatik Space* is still a small-scale exhibit that has not been regularly continued. Wang (2018) highlights the importance of Batik preservation or education to be tied closely to its participants' personal and social lives. Thus, *mBatik Space*, as a one-time event, is not able to ensure the impact of sustainability on its participants. Considering this limitation, future research could: (1) Provide a measurable scale on the impact of *mBatik Space* on participants; and (2) Expand the implementation of experiential learning framework such as *mBatik Space* to a wider audience or integrate it to the educational curriculum in order to optimize its impact in preserving the traditional skills of creating Batik.

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